

Project title: Clinical Audit Implementation in Europe - a practical and multidisciplinary approach
Project acronym: CLAUD-IT
Grant Agreement: 101160903
Call ID: EU4H-2023-PJ
Topic ID: EU4H-2023-PJ-05

CLAUD·IT

Published clinical standards relevant to radiation protection and justification of diagnostic and therapeutic procedures in radiology and nuclear medicine

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Delivery date: August 22, 2025

Version: 1.0

Dissemination level: PU

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union under the EU4Health Programme 2021–2027. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Publication name	Organisation	Year	Publicly available	Link	Citation
INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS AND RECOMMENDATIONS					
ICRP Publication 157 Ethics in radiological protection for patients in diagnosis and treatment	International Commission on Radiological Protection	2024	No	https://www.icrp.org/publication.asp?id=ICRP%20Publication%20157	ICRP, 2024. Ethics in radiological protection for patients in diagnosis and treatment. ICRP Publication 157. Ann. ICRP 53(3).
ICRP Publication 154 Optimisation of radiological protection in digital radiology techniques for medical imaging	International Commission on Radiological Protection	2023	No	https://www.icrp.org/publication.asp?id=ICRP%20Publication%20154	ICRP, 2023. Optimisation of radiological protection in digital radiology techniques for medical imaging. ICRP Publication 154. Ann. ICRP 52(3)
ICRP Publication 152 Radiation detriment calculation methodology	International Commission on Radiological Protection	2022	Yes	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/ANIB_51_3	ICRP, 2022. Radiation detriment calculation methodology. ICRP Publication 152. Ann. ICRP 51(3).
ICRP Publication 147 Use of dose quantities in radiological protection	International Commission on Radiological Protection	2021	Yes	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/ANIB_50_1	ICRP, 2021. Use of dose quantities in radiological protection. ICRP Publication 147. Ann. ICRP 50(1).
ICRP Publication 140 Radiological protection in therapy with radiopharmaceuticals	International Commission on Radiological Protection	2019	Yes	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/ANIB_48_1	ICRP, 2019. Radiological protection in therapy with radiopharmaceuticals. ICRP Publication 140. Ann. ICRP 48(1).
ICRP Publication 135 Diagnostic reference levels in medical imaging	International Commission on Radiological Protection	2017	Yes	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/ANIB_46_1	ICRP, 2017. Diagnostic reference levels in medical imaging. ICRP Publication 135. Ann. ICRP 46(1).
ICRP Publication 129 Radiological Protection in Cone	International Commission on	2015	Yes	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/ANIB_44_1	ICRP, 2015. Radiological Protection in Cone Beam Computed

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Beam Computed Tomography (CBCT)	Radiological Protection				Tomography (CBCT). ICRP Publication 129. Ann. ICRP 44(1).
ICRP Publication 128 Radiation Dose to Patients from Radiopharmaceuticals: A Compendium of Current Information Related to Frequently Used Substances	International Commission on Radiological Protection	2015	Yes	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/ANIB_44_2S	ICRP, 2015. Radiation Dose to Patients from Radiopharmaceuticals: A Compendium of Current Information Related to Frequently Used Substances. ICRP Publication 128. Ann. ICRP 44(2S).
ICRP Publication 121 Radiological protection in paediatric diagnostic and interventional radiology	International Commission on Radiological Protection	2013	Yes	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/ANIB_42_2	ICRP, 2013. Radiological protection in paediatric diagnostic and interventional radiology. ICRP Publication 121. Ann. ICRP 42(2).
ICRP Publication 120 Radiological protection in cardiology	International Commission on Radiological Protection	2013	Yes	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/ANIB_42_1	ICRP, 2013. Radiological protection in cardiology. ICRP Publication 120. Ann. ICRP 42(1).
ICRP Publication 117 Radiological Protection in Fluoroscopically Guided Procedures outside the Imaging Department	International Commission on Radiological Protection	2010	Yes	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/ANIB_40_6	ICRP, 2010. Radiological Protection in Fluoroscopically Guided Procedures outside the Imaging Department. ICRP Publication 117, Ann. ICRP 40(6).
ICRP Publication 113 Education and Training in Radiological Protection for Diagnostic and Interventional Procedures	International Commission on Radiological Protection	2009	Yes	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/ANIB_39_5	ICRP, 2009. Education and Training in Radiological Protection for Diagnostic and Interventional Procedures. ICRP Publication 113. Ann. ICRP 39 (5).
ICRP Publication 106 Radiation Dose to Patients from	International Commission on	2008	Yes	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/ANIB_38_1-2	ICRP, 2008. Radiation Dose to Patients from Radiopharmaceuticals

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Radiopharmaceuticals - Addendum 3 to ICRP Publication 53	Radiological Protection				- Addendum 3 to ICRP Publication 53. ICRP Publication 106. Ann. ICRP 38 (1-2).
ICRP Publication 105 Radiological Protection in Medicine	International Commission on Radiological Protection	2007	Yes	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/ANIB_37_6	ICRP, 2007. Radiological Protection in Medicine. ICRP Publication 105. Ann. ICRP 37 (6).
ICRP Publication 103 The 2007 Recommendations of the International Commission on Radiological Protection	International Commission on Radiological Protection	2007	Yes	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/ANIB_37_2-4	ICRP, 2007. The 2007 Recommendations of the International Commission on Radiological Protection. ICRP Publication 103. Ann. ICRP 37 (2-4).
ICRP Publication 95. Ann Doses to Infants from Ingestion of Radionuclides in Mothers' Milk	International Commission on Radiological Protection	2004	Yes	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/ANIB_34_3-4 https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/ANIB_53_1S	ICRP, 2004. Doses to Infants from Ingestion of Radionuclides in Mothers' Milk. ICRP Publication 95. Ann. ICRP 34 (3-4).
ICRP Publication 94 Release of Patients after Therapy with Unsealed Radionuclides	International Commission on Radiological Protection	2004	Yes	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/ANIB_34_2 Corrigendum https://www.icrp.org/docs/P94_Corrigenda_in_P123_Ann_ICRP_42(4).pdf	ICRP, 2004. Release of Patients after Therapy with Unsealed Radionuclides. ICRP Publication 94. Ann. ICRP 34 (2).
ICRP Publication 93 Managing Patient Dose in Digital Radiology	International Commission on	2004	Yes	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/ANIB_34_1	ICRP, 2004. Managing Patient Dose in Digital Radiology. ICRP Publication 93. Ann. ICRP 34 (1).

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	Radiological Protection				
ICRP Publication 90 Biological Effects after Prenatal Irradiation (Embryo and Fetus)	International Commission on Radiological Protection	2003	Yes	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/ANIB_33_1-2	ICRP, 2003. Biological Effects after Prenatal Irradiation (Embryo and Fetus). ICRP Publication 90. Ann. ICRP 33 (1-2).
ICRP Publication 88 Doses to the Embryo and Fetus from Intakes of Radionuclides by the Mother	International Commission on Radiological Protection	2001	Yes	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/ANIB_31_1-3	ICRP, 2001. Doses to the Embryo and Fetus from Intakes of Radionuclides by the Mother. ICRP Publication 88. Ann. ICRP 31 (1-3).
ICRP Publication 87 Managing Patient Dose in Computed Tomography	International Commission on Radiological Protection	2000	Yes	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/ANIB_30_4	ICRP, 2000. Managing Patient Dose in Computed Tomography. ICRP Publication 87. Ann. ICRP 30 (4).
ICRP Publication 85 Avoidance of Radiation Injuries from Medical Interventional Procedures.	International Commission on Radiological Protection	2000	Yes	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/ANIB_30_2	ICRP, 2000. Avoidance of Radiation Injuries from Medical Interventional Procedures. ICRP Publication 85. Ann. ICRP 30 (2).
ICRP Publication 84 Pregnancy and Medical Radiation	International Commission on Radiological Protection	2000	Yes	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/ANIB_30_1	ICRP, 2000. Pregnancy and Medical Radiation. ICRP Publication 84. Ann. ICRP 30 (1).
ICRP Publication 80 Radiation Dose to Patients from Radiopharmaceuticals (Addendum to ICRP Publication 53)	International Commission on Radiological Protection	1998	Yes	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/ANIB_28_3	ICRP, 1998. Radiation Dose to Patients from Radiopharmaceuticals (Addendum to ICRP Publication 53). ICRP Publication 80. Ann. ICRP 28 (3).

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ICRP Publication 73 Radiological Protection and Safety in Medicine	International Commission on Radiological Protection	1996	Yes	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/ANIB_26_2	ICRP, 1996. Radiological Protection and Safety in Medicine. ICRP Publication 73. Ann. ICRP 26 (2).
ICRP Publication 53 Radiation Dose to Patients from Radiopharmaceuticals	International Commission on Radiological Protection	1988	Yes	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/ANIB_18_1-4	ICRP, 1988. Radiation Dose to Patients from Radiopharmaceuticals. ICRP Publication 53. Ann. ICRP 18 (1-4).
ICRP Publication 52 Protection of the Patient in Nuclear Medicine (and Statement from the 1987 Como Meeting of ICRP)	International Commission on Radiological Protection	1987	Yes	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/ANIB_17_4	ICRP, 1987. Protection of the Patient in Nuclear Medicine (and Statement from the 1987 Como Meeting of ICRP). ICRP Publication 52. Ann. ICRP 17 (4).
ICRP Publication 44 Protection of the Patient in Radiation Therapy	International Commission on Radiological Protection	1985	Yes	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/ANIB_15_2	ICRP, 1985. Protection of the Patient in Radiation Therapy. ICRP Publication 44. Ann. ICRP 15 (2).
ICRP Publication 34 Protection of the Patient in Diagnostic Radiology	International Commission on Radiological Protection	1982	Yes	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/ANIB_9_2-3	ICRP, 1982. Protection of the Patient in Diagnostic Radiology. ICRP Publication 34. Ann. ICRP 9 (2-3).
ICRP Publication 31 Biological Effects of Inhaled Radionuclides	International Commission on Radiological Protection	1980	Yes	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/ANIB_4_1-2	ICRP, 1980. Biological Effects of Inhaled Radionuclides. ICRP Publication 31. Ann. ICRP 4 (1-2).
ICRP Publication 17 Protection of the Patient in Radionuclide Investigations	International Commission on Radiological Protection	1971	Yes	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1016/S0074-27407180001-6	ICRP, 1971. Protection of the Patient in Radionuclide Investigations. ICRP

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	Radiological Protection				Publication 17. Pergamon Press, Oxford.
ICRP Publication 16 Protection of the Patient in X-ray Diagnosis	International Commission on Radiological Protection	1970	Yes	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1016/S0074-27406980005-X	ICRP, 1970. Protection of the Patient in X-ray Diagnosis. ICRP Publication 16. Pergamon Press, Oxford.
ICRP Supporting Guidance 2 Radiation and your patient - A Guide for Medical Practitioners	International Commission on Radiological Protection	2001	Yes	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/ANIB_31_4	ICRP, 2001. Radiation and your patient - A Guide for Medical Practitioners. ICRP Supporting Guidance 2. Ann. ICRP 31 (4).
IAEA Human Health Series No. 33 QUANUM 3.0: An Updated Tool for Nuclear Medicine Audits	International Atomic Energy Agency	2021	Yes	https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/PUB1923_web.pdf	INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, QUANUM 3.0: An Updated Tool for Nuclear Medicine Audits, IAEA Human Health Series No. 33, IAEA, Vienna (2021)
IAEA Human Health Series No. 37 Nuclear Medicine Resources Manual	International Atomic Energy Agency	2020	Yes	https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/P1861_web.pdf	INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, Nuclear Medicine Resources Manual 2020 Edition, IAEA Human Health Series No. 37, IAEA, Vienna (2020)
IAEA-TECDOC-1883 Training Curriculum for Nuclear Medicine Physicians	International Atomic Energy Agency	2020	Yes	https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/TE-1883web.pdf	INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, Training Curriculum for Nuclear Medicine Physicians, IAEA-TECDOC-1883, IAEA, Vienna (2019)
IAEA Human Health Series No. 23 (Rev. 1) Nuclear Cardiology: Guidance on the	International Atomic Energy Agency	2016	Yes	https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/Pub1753web.pdf	INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, Nuclear Cardiology: Guidance on the Implementation of SPECT Myocardial Perfusion

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Implementation of SPECT Myocardial Perfusion Imaging				Corrigendum https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/Corrigenda/P1753_corrigendum.pdf	Imaging, IAEA Human Health Series No. 23 (Rev. 1), IAEA, Vienna (2016)
IAEA Human Health Series No. 43 Basics of Quality Management for Nuclear Medicine Practices	International Atomic Energy Agency	2023	Yes	https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/PUB1984_web.pdf	INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, Basics of Quality Management for Nuclear Medicine Practices, IAEA Human Health Series No. 43, IAEA, Vienna (2023)
IAEA Safety Reports Series No. 112 Patient Radiation Exposure Monitoring in Medical Imaging	International Atomic Energy Agency	2023	Yes	https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/PUB1976_web.pdf	INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, Patient Radiation Exposure Monitoring in Medical Imaging, Safety Reports Series No. 112, IAEA, Vienna (2023)
IAEA Training Course Series No. 71 Guidelines for the Certification of Clinically Qualified Medical Physicists	International Atomic Energy Agency	2021	Yes	https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/TCS-71web.pdf	INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, Guidelines for the Certification of Clinically Qualified Medical Physicists, Training Course Series No. 71, IAEA, Vienna (2021)
IAEA Safety Standards Series No. SSG-46 Radiation Protection and Safety in Medical Uses of Ionizing Radiation	International Atomic Energy Agency	2018	Yes	https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/PUB1775_web.pdf	INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, Radiation Protection and Safety in Medical Uses of Ionizing Radiation, IAEA Safety Standards Series No. SSG-46, IAEA, Vienna (2018)

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IAEA Nuclear Medicine Physics	International Atomic Energy Agency	2015	Yes	https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/Pub1617web-1294055.pdf	INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, Nuclear Medicine Physics, Non-serial Publications , IAEA, Vienna (2015)
IAEA Diagnostic Radiology Physics	International Atomic Energy Agency	2014	Yes	https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/Pub1564webNew-74666420.pdf Corrigendum https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/Corrigenda/p1564Corrigendum.pdf	INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, Diagnostic Radiology Physics, Non-serial Publications , IAEA, Vienna (2014)
IAEA Safety Standards Series No. GSR Part 3 Radiation Protection and Safety of Radiation Sources: International Basic Safety Standards,	International Atomic Energy Agency	2014	Yes	https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/Pub1578_web-57265295.pdf	EUROPEAN COMMISSION, FOOD AND AGRICULTURE ORGANIZATION OF THE UNITED NATIONS, INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, INTERNATIONAL LABOUR ORGANIZATION, OECD NUCLEAR ENERGY AGENCY, PAN AMERICAN HEALTH ORGANIZATION, UNITED NATIONS ENVIRONMENT PROGRAMME, WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION, Radiation Protection and Safety of Radiation Sources: International Basic Safety

Publication name	Organisation	Year	Publicly available	Link	Citation
					Standards, IAEA Safety Standards Series No. GSR Part 3, IAEA, Vienna (2014)
IAEA Human Health Series No. 24 Dosimetry in Diagnostic Radiology for Paediatric Patients	International Atomic Energy Agency	2014	Yes	https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/Pub1609_web.pdf	INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, Dosimetry in Diagnostic Radiology for Paediatric Patients, IAEA Human Health Series No. 24, IAEA, Vienna (2014)
IAEA Training Course Series No. 56 Postgraduate Medical Physics Academic Programmes	International Atomic Energy Agency	2013	Yes	https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/TCS-56_web.pdf	INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, Postgraduate Medical Physics Academic Programmes, Training Course Series No. 56, IAEA, Vienna (2013)
IAEA Human Health Series No. 25 Roles and Responsibilities, and Education and Training Requirements for Clinically Qualified Medical Physicists	International Atomic Energy Agency	2013	Yes	https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/Pub1610_web.pdf	INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, Roles and Responsibilities, and Education and Training Requirements for Clinically Qualified Medical Physicists, IAEA Human Health Series No. 25, IAEA, Vienna (2013)
IAEA Safety Reports Series No. 71 Radiation Protection in Paediatric Radiology	International Atomic Energy Agency	2013	Yes	https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/Pub1543_web.pdf	INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, Radiation Protection in Paediatric Radiology, Safety Reports Series No. 71, IAEA, Vienna (2013)
IAEA Training Course Series No. 50 Clinical Training of Medical Physicists Specializing in Nuclear Medicine	International Atomic Energy Agency	2011	Yes	https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/TCS-50_web.pdf	INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, Clinical Training of Medical Physicists Specializing in

Publication name	Organisation	Year	Publicly available	Link	Citation
					Nuclear Medicine, Training Course Series No. 50, IAEA, Vienna (2011)
IAEA Training Course Series No. 47 Clinical Training of Medical Physicists Specializing in Diagnostic Radiology	International Atomic Energy Agency	2010	Yes	https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/TCS-47_web.pdf	INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, Clinical Training of Medical Physicists Specializing in Diagnostic Radiology, Training Course Series No. 47, IAEA, Vienna (2010)
IAEA Human Health Series No. 4 Comprehensive Clinical Audits of Diagnostic Radiology Practices: A Tool for Quality Improvement	International Atomic Energy Agency	2010	Yes	https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/Pub1425_web.pdf	INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, Comprehensive Clinical Audits of Diagnostic Radiology Practices: A Tool for Quality Improvement, IAEA Human Health Series No. 4, IAEA, Vienna (2010)
IAEA Safety Reports Series No. 60 Radiation Protection in Newer Medical Imaging Techniques: Cardiac CT	International Atomic Energy Agency	2009	Yes	https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/pub1366_web.pdf	INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, Radiation Protection in Newer Medical Imaging Techniques: Cardiac CT, Safety Reports Series No. 60, IAEA, Vienna (2009)
IAEA Safety Reports Series No. 61 Radiation Protection in Newer Medical Imaging Techniques: CT Colonography	International Atomic Energy Agency	2009	Yes	https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/pub1367_web.pdf	INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, Radiation Protection in Newer Medical Imaging Techniques: CT Colonography, Safety Reports Series No. 61, IAEA, Vienna (2009)
IAEA Safety Reports Series No. 58 Radiation Protection in Newer Medical Imaging Techniques: PET/CT	International Atomic Energy Agency	2008	Yes	https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/pub1343_web.pdf	INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, Radiation Protection in Newer Medical Imaging Techniques:

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					PET/CT, Safety Reports Series No. 58, IAEA, Vienna (2008)
IAEA-TECDOC-1183 Management of Radioactive Waste from the Use of Radionuclides in Medicine	International Atomic Energy Agency	2000	Yes	https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/te_1183_prn.pdf	INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, Management of Radioactive Waste from the Use of Radionuclides in Medicine, IAEA-TECDOC-1183, IAEA, Vienna (2000)
IAEA Technical Reports Series No. 457 Dosimetry in Diagnostic Radiology: An International Code of Practice	International Atomic Energy Agency	2007	Yes	https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/TRS457_web.pdf	INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, Dosimetry in Diagnostic Radiology: An International Code of Practice, Technical Reports Series No. 457, IAEA, Vienna (2007)
IAEA Human Health Reports No. 5 Status of Computed Tomography Dosimetry for Wide Cone Beam Scanners	International Atomic Energy Agency	2011	Yes	https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/P1528_web.pdf https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/Corrigenda/P1528_corrigendum.pdf	INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, Status of Computed Tomography Dosimetry for Wide Cone Beam Scanners, IAEA Human Health Reports No. 5, IAEA, Vienna (2011)
IAEA Human Health Series No. 47 Handbook of Basic Quality Control Tests for Diagnostic Radiology	International Atomic Energy Agency	2023	Yes	https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/PUB2021_web.pdf	INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, Handbook of Basic Quality Control Tests for Diagnostic Radiology, IAEA Human Health Series No. 47, IAEA, Vienna (2023)
IAEA Human Health Series No. 39 Implementation of a Remote and Automated Quality Control	International Atomic Energy Agency	2021	Yes	https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/PUB1936_web.pdf	INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, Implementation of a Remote and Automated Quality

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Programme for Radiography and Mammography Equipment					Control Programme for Radiography and Mammography Equipment, IAEA Human Health Series No. 39, IAEA, Vienna (2021)
IAEA Human Health Series No. 19 Quality Assurance Programme for Computed Tomography: Diagnostic and Therapy Applications	International Atomic Energy Agency	2012	Yes	https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/Pub1557_web.pdf	INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, Quality Assurance Programme for Computed Tomography: Diagnostic and Therapy Applications, IAEA Human Health Series No. 19, IAEA, Vienna (2012)
IAEA Human Health Series No. 36 SPECT/CT Atlas of Quality Control and Image Artefacts	International Atomic Energy Agency	2019	Yes	https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/P1860_web.pdf	INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, SPECT/CT Atlas of Quality Control and Image Artefacts, IAEA Human Health Series No. 36, IAEA, Vienna (2019)
IAEA Human Health Series No. 17 Quality Assurance Programme for Digital Mammography	International Atomic Energy Agency	2011	Yes	https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/Pub1482_web.pdf	INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, Quality Assurance Programme for Digital Mammography, IAEA Human Health Series No. 17, IAEA, Vienna (2011)
IAEA-TECDOC-1968 Production and Quality Control of Fluorine-18 Labelled Radiopharmaceuticals	International Atomic Energy Agency	2021	Yes	https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/TE-1968web.pdf	INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, Production and Quality Control of Fluorine-18 Labelled Radiopharmaceuticals, IAEA-TECDOC-1968, IAEA, Vienna (2021)

Publication name	Organisation	Year	Publicly available	Link	Citation
IEC 61674:2024 CMV Medical electrical equipment - Dosimeters with ionization chambers and/or semiconductor detectors as used in X-ray diagnostic imaging	International Electrotechnical Commission	2024	No	https://products.iec.ch/view/pub/96796?q=eyJtb2RlljoiUFVCTEIQVRJT04iLCJzZWxlY3RlZEZhY2V0cyI6WyJjb21taXR0ZUUbHZsLjEuVEMgNjliXSwic29ydEJ5ljoicHVibGljYXRpb25fZGF0ZS0tZGVzYyIsImxhbmd1YWdlljoiZW4ifQ%3D%3D	IEC 61674, Medical electrical equipment - Dosimeters with ionization chambers and/or semiconductor detectors as used in X-ray diagnostic imaging, 61674:2024 CMV, IEC, Geneva, Switzerland (2024)
IEC 61223-3-8:2024 Evaluation and routine testing in medical imaging departments - Part 3-8: Acceptance and constancy tests - Imaging performance of X-ray equipment for radiography and radioscopy	International Electrotechnical Commission	2024	No	https://products.iec.ch/view/pub/64680?q=eyJtb2RlljoiUFVCTEIQVRJT04iLCJzZWxlY3RlZEZhY2V0cyI6WyJjb21taXR0ZUUbHZsLjEuVEMgNjliXSwic29ydEJ5ljoicHVibGljYXRpb25fZGF0ZS0tZGVzYyIsImxhbmd1YWdlljoiZW4ifQ%3D%3D	IEC 61223-3-8, Evaluation and routine testing in medical imaging departments - Part 3-8: Acceptance and constancy tests - Imaging performance of X-ray equipment for radiography and radioscopy, IEC, Geneva, Switzerland (2024)
IEC 60601-2-43:2022 RLV Medical electrical equipment - Part 2-43: Particular requirements for the basic safety and essential performance of X-ray equipment for interventional procedures	International Electrotechnical Commission	2022	No	https://products.iec.ch/view/pub/80753?q=eyJtb2RlljoiUFVCTEIQVRJT04iLCJzZWxlY3RlZEZhY2V0cyI6WyJjb21taXR0ZUUbHZsLjEuVEMgNjliXSwic29ydEJ5ljoicHVibGljYXRpb25fZGF0ZS0tZGVzYyIsImxhbmd1YWdlljoiZW4ifQ%3D%3D	IEC 60601-2-43, Medical electrical equipment - Part 2-43: Particular requirements for the basic safety and essential performance of X-ray equipment for interventional procedures, IEC, Geneva, Switzerland (2022)

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IEC 60601-2-54:2022 Medical electrical equipment - Part 2-54: Particular requirements for the basic safety and essential performance of X-ray equipment for radiography and radioscopy	International Electrotechnical Commission	2022	No	https://products.iec.ch/view/pub/69988?q=eyJtb2RlljoiUFVCTEIDQVRJT04iLCJzZWxLY3RlZEZhY2V0cyI6WyJjb21taXR0ZUUbHGsLjEuVEMgNjliXSwic29ydEJ5ljoicHVibGljYXRpb25fZGF0ZS0tZGVzYyIsImxhbmd1YWdlljoiZW4ifQ%3D%3D	IEC 60601-2-54, Medical electrical equipment - Part 2-54: Particular requirements for the basic safety and essential performance of X-ray equipment for radiography and radioscopy, IEC, Geneva, Switzerland (2022)
IEC 60601-2-45:2011+AMD1:2015+AMD2:2022 CSV Medical electrical equipment - Part 2-45: Particular requirements for the basic safety and essential performance of mammographic X-ray equipment and mammographic stereotactic devices	International Electrotechnical Commission	2022	No	https://products.iec.ch/view/pub/78076?q=eyJtb2RlljoiUFVCTEIDQVRJT04iLCJzZWxLY3RlZEZhY2V0cyI6WyJjb21taXR0ZUUbHGsLjEuVEMgNjliXSwic29ydEJ5ljoicHVibGljYXRpb25fZGF0ZS0tZGVzYyIsImxhbmd1YWdlljoiZW4ifQ%3D%3D	IEC 60601-2-45:2011+AMD1:2015+AMD2, Medical electrical equipment - Part 2-45: Particular requirements for the basic safety and essential performance of mammographic X-ray equipment and mammographic stereotactic devices, IEC, Geneva, Switzerland (2022)
IEC 61675-1:2022 RLV Radionuclide imaging devices - Characteristics and test conditions - Part 1: Positron emission tomographs	International Electrotechnical Commission	2022	No	https://products.iec.ch/view/pub/75011?q=eyJtb2RlljoiUFVCTEIDQVRJT04iLCJzZWxLY3RlZEZhY2V0cyI6WyJjb21taXR0ZUUbHGsLjEuVEMgNjliXSwic29ydEJ5ljoicHVibGljYXRpb25fZGF0ZS0tZGVzYyIsImxhbmd1YWdlljoiZW4ifQ%3D%3D	IEC 61675-1, Radionuclide imaging devices - Characteristics and test conditions - Part 1: Positron emission tomographs, IEC, Geneva, Switzerland (2022)

Publication name	Organisation	Year	Publicly available	Link	Citation
IEC 61223-3-7:2021 Evaluation and routine testing in medical imaging departments - Part 3-7: Acceptance and constancy tests - Imaging performance of X-ray equipment for dental cone beam computed tomography	International Electrotechnical Commission	2021	No	https://products.iec.ch/view/pub/62975?q=eyJtb2RlljoiUFVCTEIDQVRJT04iLCJzZWxlY3RlZEFhY2V0cyI6WyJjb21taXR0ZlUUbHZsLjEuVEMgNjliXSwic29ydEJ5ljoicHVibGljYXRpb25fZGF0ZS0tZGVzYyIsImxhbmd1YWdlljoiZW4ifQ%3D%3D	IEC 61223-3-7, Evaluation and routine testing in medical imaging departments - Part 3-7: Acceptance and constancy tests - Imaging performance of X-ray equipment for dental cone beam computed tomography, IEC, Geneva, Switzerland (2021)
IEC 62563-2:2021 Medical electrical equipment - Medical image display systems - Part 2: Acceptance and constancy tests for medical image displays	International Electrotechnical Commission	2021	No	https://products.iec.ch/view/pub/62979?q=eyJtb2RlljoiUFVCTEIDQVRJT04iLCJzZWxlY3RlZEFhY2V0cyI6WyJjb21taXR0ZlUUbHZsLjEuVEMgNjliXSwic29ydEJ5ljoicHVibGljYXRpb25fZGF0ZS0tZGVzYyIsImxhbmd1YWdlljoiZW4ifQ%3D%3D	IEC 62563-2, Medical electrical equipment - Medical image display systems - Part 2: Acceptance and constancy tests for medical image displays, IEC, Geneva, Switzerland (2021)
IEC 62563-1:2009+AMD1:2016+AMD2:2021 CSV Medical electrical equipment - Medical image display systems - Part 1: Evaluation methods	International Electrotechnical Commission	2021	No	https://products.iec.ch/view/pub/70108?q=eyJtb2RlljoiUFVCTEIDQVRJT04iLCJzZWxlY3RlZEFhY2V0cyI6WyJjb21taXR0ZlUUbHZsLjEuVEMgNjliXSwic29ydEJ5ljoicHVibGljYXRpb25fZGF0ZS0tZGVzYyIsImxhbmd1YWdlljoiZW4ifQ%3D%3D	IEC 62563-1:2009+AMD1:2016+AMD2, Medical electrical equipment - Medical image display systems - Part 1: Evaluation methods, IEC, Geneva, Switzerland (2021)

Publication name	Organisation	Year	Publicly available	Link	Citation
IEC 62563-1:2009/AMD2:2021 Amendment 2 - Medical electrical equipment - Medical image display systems - Part 1: Evaluation methods	International Electrotechnical Commission	2021	No	https://products.iec.ch/view/pub/65415?q=eyJtb2RlljoiUFVCTEIDQVRJT04iLCJzZWxlY3RlZEZhY2V0cyI6WyJjb21taXR0ZUWUubHZsLjEuVEMgNjliXSwic29ydEJ5ljoicHVibGljYXRpb25fZGF0ZS0tZGVzYyIsImxhbmd1YWdlljoiZW4ifQ%3D%3D	IEC 62563-1:2009/AMD2, Amendment 2 - Medical electrical equipment - Medical image display systems - Part 1: Evaluation methods, IEC, Geneva, Switzerland (2021)
IEC 60601-2-63:2012+AMD1:2017+AMD2:2021 CSV Medical electrical equipment - Part 2-63: Particular requirements for the basic safety and essential performance of dental extra-oral X-ray equipment	International Electrotechnical Commission	2021	No	https://products.iec.ch/view/pub/68977?q=eyJtb2RlljoiUFVCTEIDQVRJT04iLCJzZWxlY3RlZEZhY2V0cyI6WyJjb21taXR0ZUWUubHZsLjEuVEMgNjliXSwic29ydEJ5ljoicHVibGljYXRpb25fZGF0ZS0tZGVzYyIsImxhbmd1YWdlljoiZW4ifQ%3D%3D	IEC 60601-2-63:2012+AMD1:2017+AMD2, Medical electrical equipment - Part 2-63: Particular requirements for the basic safety and essential performance of dental extra-oral X-ray equipment, IEC, Geneva, Switzerland (2021)
IEC 60601-2-63:2012/AMD2:2021 Amendment 2 - Medical electrical equipment - Part 2-63: Particular requirements for the basic safety and essential performance of dental extra-oral X-ray equipment	International Electrotechnical Commission	2021	No	https://products.iec.ch/view/pub/64673?q=eyJtb2RlljoiUFVCTEIDQVRJT04iLCJzZWxlY3RlZEZhY2V0cyI6WyJjb21taXR0ZUWUubHZsLjEuVEMgNjliXSwic29ydEJ5ljoicHVibGljYXRpb25fZGF0ZS0tZGVzYyIsImxhbmd1YWdlljoiZW4ifQ%3D%3D	IEC 60601-2-63:2012/AMD2, Amendment 2 - Medical electrical equipment - Part 2-63: Particular requirements for the basic safety and essential performance of dental extra-oral X-ray equipment, IEC, Geneva, Switzerland (2021)

Publication name	Organisation	Year	Publicly available	Link	Citation
IEC 63073-1:2020 Dedicated radionuclide imaging devices - Characteristics and test conditions - Part 1: Cardiac SPECT	International Electrotechnical Commission	2020	No	https://products.iec.ch/view/pub/28799?q=eyJtb2RlljoiUFVCTEIDQVRJT04iLCJzZWx1Y3RlZEZhY2V0cyI6WyJjb21taXR0ZUWUubHZsLjEuVEMgNjliXSwic29ydEJ5ljoicHVibGljYXRpb25fZGF0ZS0tZGVzYyIsImxhbmd1YWdlljoiZW4ifQ%3D%3D	IEC 63073-1, Dedicated radionuclide imaging devices - Characteristics and test conditions - Part 1: Cardiac SPECT, IEC, Geneva, Switzerland (2020)
IEC 61223-3-6:2020 Evaluation and routine testing in medical imaging departments - Part 3-6: Acceptance and constancy tests - Imaging performance of mammographic X-ray equipment used in a mammographic tomosynthesis mode of operation	International Electrotechnical Commission	2020	No	https://products.iec.ch/view/pub/59955?q=eyJtb2RlljoiUFVCTEIDQVRJT04iLCJzZWx1Y3RlZEZhY2V0cyI6WyJjb21taXR0ZUWUubHZsLjEuVEMgNjliXSwic29ydEJ5ljoicHVibGljYXRpb25fZGF0ZS0tZGVzYyIsImxhbmd1YWdlljoiZW4ifQ%3D%3D	IEC 61223-3-6, Evaluation and routine testing in medical imaging departments - Part 3-6: Acceptance and constancy tests - Imaging performance of mammographic X-ray equipment used in a mammographic tomosynthesis mode of operation IEC, Geneva, Switzerland (2020)
ISO 14971:2019 Medical devices - Application of risk management to medical devices	International Electrotechnical Commission/ International Organization for Standardization	2019	No	https://products.iec.ch/view/pub/60565?q=eyJtb2RlljoiUFVCTEIDQVRJT04iLCJzZWx1Y3RlZEZhY2V0cyI6WyJjb21taXR0ZUWUubHZsLjEuVEMgNjliXSwic29ydEJ5ljoicHVibGljYXRpb25fZGF0ZS0tZGVzYyIsImxhbmd1YWdlljoiZW4ifQ%3D%3D	ISO 14971, Medical devices - Application of risk management to medical devices ISO, Geneva, Switzerland (2019)

Publication name	Organisation	Year	Publicly available	Link	Citation
IEC 61223-3-5:2019 Evaluation and routine testing in medical imaging departments - Part 3-5: Acceptance and constancy tests - Imaging performance of computed tomography X-ray equipment	International Electrotechnical Commission	2019	No	https://products.iec.ch/view/pub/59789?q=eyJtb2RlljoiUFVCTEIDQVRJT04iLCJzZWxlY3RlZEZhY2V0cyI6WyJjb21taXR0ZUWUubHZsLjEuVEMgNjliXSwic29ydEJ5ljoicHVibGljYXRpb25fZGF0ZS0tZGVzYyIsImxhbmd1YWdlljoiZW4ifQ%3D%3D	IEC 61223-3-5, Evaluation and routine testing in medical imaging departments - Part 3-5: Acceptance and constancy tests - Imaging performance of computed tomography X-ray equipment, IEC, Geneva, Switzerland (2019)
IEC 62985:2019 Methods for calculating size specific dose estimates (SSDE) for computed tomography	International Electrotechnical Commission	2019	No	https://products.iec.ch/view/pub/29540?q=eyJtb2RlljoiUFVCTEIDQVRJT04iLCJzZWxlY3RlZEZhY2V0cyI6WyJjb21taXR0ZUWUubHZsLjEuVEMgNjliXSwic29ydEJ5ljoicHVibGljYXRpb25fZGF0ZS0tZGVzYyIsImxhbmd1YWdlljoiZW4ifQ%3D%3D	IEC 62985, Methods for calculating size specific dose estimates (SSDE) for computed tomography, IEC, Geneva, Switzerland (2019)
IEC TR 61948-2:2019 Nuclear medicine instrumentation - Routine tests - Part 2: Scintillation cameras and single photon emission computed tomography imaging	International Electrotechnical Commission	2019	No	https://products.iec.ch/view/pub/61406?q=eyJtb2RlljoiUFVCTEIDQVRJT04iLCJzZWxlY3RlZEZhY2V0cyI6WyJjb21taXR0ZUWUubHZsLjEuVEMgNjliXSwic29ydEJ5ljoicHVibGljYXRpb25fZGF0ZS0tZGVzYyIsImxhbmd1YWdlljoiZW4ifQ%3D%3D	IEC TR 61948-2, Nuclear medicine instrumentation - Routine tests - Part 2: Scintillation cameras and single photon emission computed tomography imaging, IEC, Geneva, Switzerland (2019)

Publication name	Organisation	Year	Publicly available	Link	Citation
IEC 80601-2-60:2019 Medical electrical equipment - Part 2-60: Particular requirements for the basic safety and essential performance of dental equipment	International Electrotechnical Commission	2019	No	https://products.iec.ch/view/pub/27876?q=eyJtb2RlljoiUFVCTEIQVVRJT04iLCJzZWxlY3RlZEZhY2V0cyI6WyJjb21taXR0ZUWUubHZsLjEuVEMgNjliXSwic29ydEJ5ljoicHVibGljYXRpb25fZGF0ZS0tZGVzYyIsImxhbmd1YWdlljoiZW4ifQ%3D%3D	IEC 80601-2-60, Medical electrical equipment - Part 2-60: Particular requirements for the basic safety and essential performance of dental equipment, IEC, Geneva, Switzerland (2019)
IEC TR 61948-4:2019 Nuclear medicine instrumentation - Routine tests - Part 4: Radionuclide calibrators	International Electrotechnical Commission	2019	No	https://products.iec.ch/view/pub/61407?q=eyJtb2RlljoiUFVCTEIQVVRJT04iLCJzZWxlY3RlZEZhY2V0cyI6WyJjb21taXR0ZUWUubHZsLjEuVEMgNjliXSwic29ydEJ5ljoicHVibGljYXRpb25fZGF0ZS0tZGVzYyIsImxhbmd1YWdlljoiZW4ifQ%3D%3D	IEC TR 61948-4, Nuclear medicine instrumentation - Routine tests - Part 4: Radionuclide calibrators, IEC, Geneva, Switzerland (2019)
IEC TR 61948-3:2018 Nuclear medicine instrumentation - Routine tests - Part 3: Positron emission tomographs	International Electrotechnical Commission	2018	No	https://products.iec.ch/view/pub/60788?q=eyJtb2RlljoiUFVCTEIQVVRJT04iLCJzZWxlY3RlZEZhY2V0cyI6WyJjb21taXR0ZUWUubHZsLjEuVEMgNjliXSwic29ydEJ5ljoicHVibGljYXRpb25fZGF0ZS0tZGVzYyIsImxhbmd1YWdlljoiZW4ifQ%3D%3D	IEC TR 61948-3, Nuclear medicine instrumentation - Routine tests - Part 3: Positron emission tomographs, IEC, Geneva, Switzerland (2019)
EU RECOMMENDATIONS AND GUIDELINES					

Publication name	Organisation	Year	Publicly available	Link	Citation
RP 206 Guidance on the implementation of Council Directive 2013/59/Euratom Requirements for Medical Equipment with Respect to Monitoring and Control of Patient Radiation Exposures	European Commission	2025	Yes	https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/8d98ab9a-fef5-11ef-9503-01aa75ed71a1/language-en	European Commission: Directorate-General for Energy, NucAdvisor/EFOMP, Mario N., Andersson J., Lopez Medina A., Visvikis D., Kolmayer A., Frija G.. Guidance on the implementation of Council Directive 2013/59/Euratom Requirements for Medical Equipment with Respect to Monitoring and Control of Patient Radiation Exposures : final report. Publications Office of the European Union; 2025. Available from: doi/10.2833/5894651
RP 205 European co-ordinated action on improving justification of computed tomography	European Commission	2024	Yes	https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/dc071d95-7179-11ef-a8ba-01aa75ed71a1	European Commission: Directorate-General for Energy, Brkljačić B., Karoussou-Schreiner A., Sosna J., Foley S., Bly R., Brady A. et al. European co-ordinated action on improving justification of computed tomography : results and recommendations from a first-time multi-national study on CT justification in the EU. Publications Office of the European Union; 2024. Available from: doi/10.2833/80267
RP 198 Current status and recommendations for	European Commission	2024	Yes	https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-	European Commission: Directorate-General for Energy, Howlett D.,

Publication name	Organisation	Year	Publicly available	Link	Citation
improving uptake and implementation of clinical audit of medical radiological procedures (QuADRANT, a European study on clinical audit of medical radiological procedures)				/publication/94c09d1b-9230-11ed-b508-01aa75ed71a1	Giammarile F., Jornet N., Hierath M., Clark J.. Current status and recommendations for improving uptake and implementation of clinical audit of medical radiological procedures : QuADRANT, a European study on clinical audit of medical radiological procedures. Publications Office of the European Union; 2022. Available from: doi/10.2833/468186
RP 196 Health issues after radiation exposure at young age: EU Scientific Seminar 2020	European Commission	2021	Yes	https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/3680f215-63a0-11ec-9136-01aa75ed71a1/language-en	European Commission: Directorate-General for Energy, ‘Radiosensitivity’ of children : health issues after radiation exposure at young age : EU Scientific Seminar 2020. Publications Office of the European Union; 2021. Available from: doi/10.2833/769468
RP 195 European study on clinical diagnostic reference levels for X-ray medical imaging (EUCLID)	European Commission	2021	Yes	https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/a78331f7-7199-11eb-9ac9-01aa75ed71a1/language-en?WT.mc_id=Searchresult&WT.ria_c=37085&WT.ria_f=3608&WT.ria_ev=search	European Commission: Directorate-General for Energy, Damilakis, J., Frija, G., Jaschke, W., Paulo, G. et al., European study on clinical diagnostic reference levels for X-ray medical imaging – EUCLID, Publications Office of the European Union, 2021,

Publication name	Organisation	Year	Publicly available	Link	Citation
					https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2833/452154
RP 185 European guidelines on diagnostic reference levels for paediatric imaging	European Commission	2018	Yes	https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/6e473ff5-bd4b-11e8-99ee-01aa75ed71a1	European Commission: Directorate-General for Energy, European guidelines on diagnostic reference levels for paediatric imaging. Publications Office; 2018. Available from: doi/10.2833/486256
RP 180 Medical radiation exposure of the European population	European Commission	2018	Yes	https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/d2c4b535-1d96-4d8c-b715-2d03fc927fc9	European Commission: Directorate-General for Energy, Medical radiation exposure of the European population. Publications Office; 2015. Available from: doi/10.2833/708119
RP 175 Guidelines on radiation protection education and training of medical professionals in the European Union	European Commission	2014	Yes	https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/9020ff7f-e7c6-4c11-a0f5-50449beeba0b Corrigendum https://circabc.europa.eu/ui/group/8f5f9424-a7ef-4dbf-b914-1af1d12ff5d2/library/3e2aaa97-58e8-4c41-b254-14798dc0533f/details?download=true	European Commission: Directorate-General for Energy, Guidelines on radiation protection education and training of medical professionals in the European Union. Publications Office; 2014. Available from: doi/10.2833/19786

Publication name	Organisation	Year	Publicly available	Link	Citation
RP 174 European guidelines on medical physics expert	European Commission	2014	Yes	<p>https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/b82ed768-4c50-4c9a-a789-98a3b0df5391</p> <p>Annex 1 https://circabc.europa.eu/ui/group/8f5f9424-a7ef-4dbf-b914-1af1d12ff5d2/library/955bca53-043f-4811-9bdb-8a560282c924/details?download=true</p> <p>Annex 2 https://circabc.europa.eu/ui/group/8f5f9424-a7ef-4dbf-b914-1af1d12ff5d2/library/dec4f061-6371-496a-9090-437a6a262032/details?download=true</p> <p>Corrigendum https://circabc.europa.eu/ui/group/8f5f9424-a7ef-4dbf-b914-1af1d12ff5d2/library/83d128a</p>	European Commission: Directorate-General for Energy, Putten W. v. d., Caruana C. J., Evans S., Guibelalde E., Christofides S.. European guidelines on medical physics expert. Publications Office; 2014. Available from: doi/10.2833/18393

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				5-7dff-4fb8-83cf-bac56d974691/details?download=true	
RP 172 Cone beam CT for dental and maxillofacial radiology - Evidence-based guidelines	European Commission	2012	Yes	https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/ec5936c7-5a29-4a93-9b3a-01a5d78d7b2e	European Commission: Directorate-General for Energy, Cone beam CT for dental and maxillofacial radiology : evidence-based guidelines. Publications Office; 2012. Available from: doi/10.2768/21874
RP 159 European Commission guidelines on clinical audit for medical radiological practices (diagnostic radiology, nuclear medicine and radiotherapy)	European Commission	2009	Yes	https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/75688cc6-c9d3-4c43-9bfd-ce5cea0d8bcb	European Commission: Directorate-General for Energy and Transport, European Commission guidelines on clinical audit for medical radiological practices (diagnostic radiology, nuclear medicine and radiotherapy) . Publications Office; 2009. Available from: doi/10.2768/20266
RP 154 European guidance on estimating population doses from medical x-ray procedures	European Commission	2009	Yes	https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/72d806a2-2fb4-4e4d-a845-3b276feed8eb	European Commission: Directorate-General for Energy and Transport, Health Protection Agency. Centre for Radiation Chemical and Environmental Hazards (UK), European guidance on estimating population doses from medical x-ray procedures . Publications Office;

Publication name	Organisation	Year	Publicly available	Link	Citation
					2008. Available from: doi/10.2768/38190
RP 131 Effects of in utero exposure to ionising radiation during the early phases of pregnancy	European Commission	2002	Yes	https://circabc.europa.eu/ui/group/8f5f9424-a7ef-4dbf-b914-1af1d12ff5d2/library/c4e0ad40-67e2-4c96-9218-5b1e2c9ed03a/details?download=true	Commission of the European Communities. Directorate-General for Nuclear Safety and Safeguards. Effects of in Utero Exposure to Ionising Radiation During the Early Phases of Pregnancy. Office for Official Publications of the European Communities, 2002.
RP 118 Referral guidelines for imaging	European Commission	2001	Yes	<p>https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/ac475fa0-09b6-4430-a3a3-6edef21df2e6</p> <p>Update 2003: https://circabc.europa.eu/ui/group/8f5f9424-a7ef-4dbf-b914-1af1d12ff5d2/library/36413fcf-f497-4b08-89ca-456030ae45fc/details?download=true</p> <p>Annex: https://circabc.europa.eu/ui/group/8f5f9424-a7ef-4dbf-b914-</p>	European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, The Royal College of Radiologists (London), Dixon A.. Referral guidelines for imaging : radiation protection No 118. Publications Office of the European Union; 2001

Publication name	Organisation	Year	Publicly available	Link	Citation
				1af1d12ff5d2/library/aa55a52f-75f4-4612-9b72-bc7d365964f3/details?download=true	
RP 116 Guidelines on education and training in radiation protection for medical exposures	European Commission	2000	Yes	https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/41d430b5-97f0-4c39-8542-dacb6a3fa959	European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, Guidelines on education and training in radiation protection for medical exposures. Publications Office; 2000.
RP 109 Guidance on diagnostic reference levels (DRLs) for medical exposures	European Commission	1999	Yes	https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/7a29147a-9545-4a44-b6d3-14310e28cff5	European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, Guidance on diagnostic reference levels (DRLs) for medical exposures. Publications Office; 1999.
RP 100 Guidance for protection of unborn children and infants irradiated due to parental medical exposures	European Commission	1999	Yes	https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/8cff6e4-e7da-4d88-b810-ff343512f2a3	European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, Guidance for protection of unborn children and infants irradiated due to parental medical exposures. Publications Office; 1999.
RP 97 Radiation protection following iodine-131 therapy (exposures due to outpatients or discharged inpatients)	European Commission	1998	Yes	https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/cf28c3bc-dff4-4602-95dd-1d0bfb7c8fcc	European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, Radiation protection following iodine-131 therapy (exposures due to outpatients or discharged inpatients). Publications Office; 1998.

Publication name	Organisation	Year	Publicly available	Link	Citation
COMMISSION RECOMMENDATION (EU) 2024/1112 of 18 April 2024 on clinical audits of medical radiological practices carried out pursuant to Council Directive 2013/59/Euratom	European Commission	2024	Yes	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=OJ:L_202401112	
EC Conclusions: Justification on medical imaging involving exposure to ionising radiation	The Council of the European Union	2015	Yes	https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-14617-2015-INIT/en/pdf	
EU LEGISLATIVE					
Council Directive 2013/59/Euratom of 5 December 2013 laying down basic safety standards for protection against the dangers arising from exposure to ionising radiation, and repealing Directives 89/618/Euratom, 90/641/Euratom, 96/29/Euratom, 97/43/Euratom and 2003/122/Euratom	The Council of the European Union	2013	Yes	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32013L0059&qid=1747903007053 Corrigendum 2 https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32013L0059R%2804%29&qid=1747903007053 Corrigendum 1 https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32013L0059R%2804%29&qid=1747903007053	

Publication name	Organisation	Year	Publicly available	Link	Citation
				3A32013L0059R%2802%29&qid=1747903007053	
PROFESSIONAL SOCIETIES					
ESR's Guide to Clinical Audit – AUDITRAD (Esperanto 4th Edition)	ECR & CLAUD-IT EU4Health project	2025	Yes	https://www.myesr.org/app/uploads/2025/03/2025_Esperanto-ESR-Guide-to-Clinical-Audit-in-Radiology-4th-20-02.pdf	
NuCline ESPERANTO for Nuclear Medicine	CLAUD-IT EU4Health project	2025	Yes	https://www.eibir.org/app/uploads/NuCline_CLAUD-IT_eBook.pdf	
European consensus on patient contact shielding	EFOMP EFRS ESR ESPR EuroSafe Imaging EURADOS EADMFR	2021	Yes	https://insightsimaging.springeropen.com/counter/pdf/10.1186/s13244-021-01085-4.pdf	Hiles P, Gilligan P, Damilakis J, Briers E, Candela-Juan C, Faj D, Foley S, Frija G, Granata C, de Las Heras Gala H, Pauwels R, Sans Merce M, Simantirakis G, Vano E. European consensus on patient contact shielding. Insights Imaging. 2021 Dec 23;12(1):194. doi:10.1186/s13244-021-01085-4
ACR–AAPM technical standard for diagnostic medical physics performance monitoring of fluoroscopic equipment	ACR/AAPM	2021	Yes	https://gravitas.acr.org/PPTS/GetDocumentView?docId=117	ACR–AAPM, Technical standard for diagnostic medical physics performance monitoring of fluoroscopic equipment, ACR/AAPM (2021)

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ACR–AAPM technical standard for diagnostic medical physics performance monitoring of radiographic equipment	ACR/AAPM	2021	Yes	https://gravitas.acr.org/PPTS/GetDocumentView?docId=120	ACR–AAPM, Technical standard for diagnostic medical physics performance monitoring of radiographic equipment (2021)
ACR–AAPM technical standard for diagnostic medical physics performance monitoring of computed tomography (CT) equipment	ACR/AAPM	2022	Yes	https://gravitas.acr.org/PPTS/GetDocumentView?docId=131	ACR–AAPM, Technical standard for diagnostic medical physics performance monitoring of computed tomography (CT) equipment (2022)
ACR–AAPM technical standard for management of the use of radiation in fluoroscopic procedures	ACR/AAPM	2023	Yes	https://gravitas.acr.org/PPTS/GetDocumentView?docId=197	ACR–AAPM, Technical standard for management of the use of radiation in fluoroscopic procedures (2023)
ACR–AAPM technical standard for nuclear medical physics performance monitoring of gamma cameras	ACR/AAPM	2023	Yes	https://gravitas.acr.org/PPTS/GetDocumentView?docId=196	ACR–AAPM, Technical standard for nuclear medical physics performance monitoring of gamma cameras (2023)
ACR–AAPM technical standard for medical physics performance monitoring of PET/CT imaging equipment	ACR/AAPM	2023	Yes	https://gravitas.acr.org/PPTS/GetDocumentView?docId=198	ACR–AAPM, Technical standard for medical physics performance monitoring of PET/CT imaging equipment (2023)
ACR–AAPM technical standard for medical physics performance monitoring of SPECT/CT equipment	ACR/AAPM	2023	Yes	https://gravitas.acr.org/PPTS/GetDocumentView?docId=211	ACR–AAPM, Technical standard for medical physics performance monitoring of SPECT/CT equipment (2023)
ACR practice parameter for the performance of digital breast tomosynthesis (DBT)	ACR	2023	Yes	https://gravitas.acr.org/PPTS/GetDocumentView?docId=7	ACR, Practice parameter for the performance of digital breast tomosynthesis (DBT) (2023)

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ACR practice parameter for the performance of screening and diagnostic mammography	ACR	2023	Yes	https://gravitas.acr.org/PPTS/GetDocumentView?docId=8	ACR, Practice parameter for the performance of screening and diagnostic mammography (2023)
ACR–SABI–SPR–STR practice parameter for the performance of thoracic computed tomography (CT)	ACR	2023	Yes	https://gravitas.acr.org/PPTS/GetDocumentView?docId=13	ACR–SABI–SPR–STR, Practice parameter for the performance of thoracic computed tomography (CT) (2023)
ACR–AAPM–SPR practice parameter for diagnostic reference levels and achievable doses in medical x-ray imaging	ACR	2023	Yes	https://gravitas.acr.org/PPTS/GetDocumentView?docId=16	ACR–AAPM–SPR, Practice parameter for diagnostic reference levels and achievable doses in medical x-ray imaging (2023)
ACR–SIR–SNIS–SPR practice parameter for the clinical practice of interventional radiology	ACR	2024	Yes	https://gravitas.acr.org/PPTS/GetDocumentView?docId=36	ACR–SIR–SNIS–SPR, Practice parameter for the clinical practice of interventional radiology (2024)
ACR practice parameter for communication of diagnostic imaging findings	ACR	2020	Yes	https://gravitas.acr.org/PPTS/GetDocumentView?docId=74	ACR, Practice parameter for communication of diagnostic imaging findings (2020)
ACR–ASER–SCBT–MR–SPR practice parameter for the performance of pediatric computed tomography (CT)	ACR	2019	Yes	https://gravitas.acr.org/PPTS/GetDocumentView?docId=77	ACR–ASER–SCBT–MR–SPR, Practice parameter for the performance of pediatric computed tomography (CT) (2019)
ACR–AAPM–ACNM–SNMMI practice parameter for reference levels and achievable administered activity for nuclear medicine and molecular imaging	ACR	2020	Yes	https://gravitas.acr.org/PPTS/GetDocumentView?docId=94	ACR–AAPM–ACNM–SNMMI, Practice parameter for reference levels and achievable administered activity for nuclear medicine and molecular imaging (2020)

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ACR–SPR practice parameter for performing and interpreting diagnostic computed tomography (CT)	ACR	2022	Yes	https://gravitas.acr.org/PPTS/GetDocumentView?docId=132	ACR–SPR, Practice parameter for performing and interpreting diagnostic computed tomography (CT) (2022)
ACR–AAPM–SIIM practice parameter for determinants of image quality in mammography	ACR	2022	Yes	https://gravitas.acr.org/PPTS/GetDocumentView?docId=140	ACR–AAPM–SIIM, Practice parameter for determinants of image quality in mammography (2022)
ACR–ASNR–SPR practice parameter for the performance of computed tomography (CT) in the evaluation and classification of traumatic brain injury	ACR	2022	Yes	https://gravitas.acr.org/PPTS/GetDocumentView?docId=156	ACR–ASNR–SPR, Practice parameter for the performance of computed tomography (CT) in the evaluation and classification of traumatic brain injury (2022)
ACR–SABI–SAR–SPR practice parameter for the performance of computed tomography (CT) of the abdomen and computed tomography (CT) of the pelvis	ACR	2021	Yes	https://gravitas.acr.org/PPTS/GetDocumentView?docId=168	ACR–SABI–SAR–SPR, Practice parameter for the performance of computed tomography (CT) of the abdomen and computed tomography (CT) of the pelvis (2021)
ACR–ACNM–SNMMI–SPR practice parameter for the use of radiopharmaceuticals in diagnostic procedures	ACR	2021	Yes	https://gravitas.acr.org/PPTS/GetDocumentView?docId=171	ACR–ACNM–SNMMI–SPR, Practice parameter for the use of radiopharmaceuticals in diagnostic procedures (2021)
ACR–ACNM–SNMMI–SPR practice parameter for performing FDG-PET/CT in oncology	ACR	2021	Yes	https://gravitas.acr.org/PPTS/GetDocumentView?docId=173	ACR–ACNM–SNMMI–SPR, Practice parameter for performing FDG-PET/CT in oncology (2021)

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ACR–SPR practice parameter for imaging pregnant or potentially pregnant patients with ionizing radiation	ACR	2023	Yes	https://gravitas.acr.org/PPTS/GetDocumentView?docId=23	ACR–SPR, Practice parameter for imaging pregnant or potentially pregnant patients with ionizing radiation (2023)
ACR–SABI–SAR practice parameter for the performance of computed tomography (CT) colonography in adults	ACR	2024	Yes	https://gravitas.acr.org/PPTS/GetDocumentView?docId=33	ACR–SABI–SAR, Practice parameter for the performance of computed tomography (CT) colonography in adults (2024)
EANM Guidelines	EANM		Yes	https://eanm.org/publications/guidelines/overview/	
EFOMP Protocol: Quality Control of Dynamic X-ray Imaging Systems	EFOMP	2024	Yes	https://www.efomp.org/uploads/be68860f-5f48-4450-9d96-27dc634a32a6/Angio%20QC%20Protocol_v4.pdf	European Federation of Organisations for Medical Physics Working Group on “Angiographic and fluoroscopic systems – QC protocol”. Quality control of dynamic X-ray imaging systems (Angio QC Protocol v 4). EFOMP; Version 01.2024, published April 18 2024.
EFOMP Protocol: Quality Control in PET/CT and PET/MR	EFOMP	2023	Yes	https://www.efomp.org/uploads/10fd24d1-354d-48d6-bf8f-e93e98cb7d81/EFOMP%E2%80%99S%20GUIDELINE%20QUALITY%20CONTROLS%20IN%20PETCT%20AND%20PETMR.pdf	European Federation of Organisations for Medical Physics. EFOMP’s guideline: quality controls in PET/CT and PET/MR. EFOMP; 2023.

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EFOMP Protocol: Quality Control in Digital Breast Tomosynthesis (DBT)	EFOMP	2023	Yes	https://www.efomp.org/uploads/dc3ee6f3-1528-4379-9a32-e2414283218b/QUALITY%20CONTROL%20IN%20DIGITAL%20BREAST%20TOMOSYNTHESIS%20(DBT)_F4.pdf	European Federation of Organisations for Medical Physics. Quality Control in Digital Breast Tomosynthesis (DBT): EFOMP protocol. EFOMP; Version 01.03.2023.
EFOMP-ESTRO-IAEA Protocol: Quality control in cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT)	EFOMP/ESTRO/IAEA	2019	Yes	https://www.efomp.org/uploads/2d23d153-b77c-4161-802c-5b8422d15e29/EFOMP_IAEA_ESTRO_%20CBCT_2019_05_27.pdf	European Federation of Organisations for Medical Physics; ESTRO; IAEA. Quality control in cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT): EFOMP-ESTRO-IAEA protocol. EFOMP; 2nd edition, May 27 2019.
EFOMP Mammo Protocol	EFOMP	2017	Yes	http://dx.medra.org/10.19285/MAMMOEFOMP.V1.0.2015.03	European Federation of Organisations for Medical Physics. EFOMP Mammo Protocol; 2017.
CIRSE Standards of Quality Assurance in Interventional Oncology	CIRSE	2018	Yes	https://www.iasios.org/accreditation/standards-of-qa/	CIRSE Standards of Practice Committee. CIRSE standards of quality assurance in interventional oncology. Vienna: Cardiovascular and Interventional Radiological Society of Europe; 2018.
European recommendations on practices in pediatric neuroradiology: consensus document from the European	European Society of Neuroradiology (ESNR)/Europea	2023	Yes	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36063184/	Rossi A, Argyropoulou M, Zlatareva D, Boulouis G, Pizzini FB, van den Hauwe L, Raissaki M, Pruvo JP, Rosendahl K, Hoffmann C, Sundgren

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Society of Neuroradiology (ESNR), European Society of Paediatric Radiology (ESPR) and European Union of Medical Specialists Division of Neuroradiology (UEMS)	n Society of Paediatric Radiology (ESPR)/European Union of Medical Specialists Division of Neuroradiology (UEMS)				PC; ESNR Pediatric Neuroradiology Subspecialty Committee; ESPR Neuroradiology Taskforce. European recommendations on practices in pediatric neuroradiology: consensus document from the European Society of Neuroradiology (ESNR), European Society of Paediatric Radiology (ESPR) and European Union of Medical Specialists Division of Neuroradiology (UEMS). <i>Pediatr Radiol.</i> 2023 Jan;53(1):159-168
OTHER					
ICRP Glossary	ICRP	2025	Yes	https://icrpaedia.org/ICRP_Glossary	
INITIATIVES/CAMPAIGNS					
IAEA Bonn call for action	IAEA	2012	Yes	https://www.iaea.org/sites/default/files/17/12/bonn-call-for-action.pdf	
EuroSafe Imaging Call for Action	ESR	2018	Yes	https://www.eurosafeimaging.org/about/call-for-action	
Image Wisely	American College of Radiology (ACR) Radiological Society of North America (RSNA)		Yes	https://www.imagewisely.org/	

Publication name	Organisation	Year	Publicly available	Link	Citation
	American Society of Radiologic Technologists (ASRT) American Association of Physicists in Medicine (AAPM)				
Image Gently	The Society for Pediatric Radiology (SPR) American Association of Physicists in Medicine (AAPM) American College of Radiology (ACR) American Society of Radiologic Technologists (ASRT)		Yes	https://www.imagegently.org/	